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Choosing the appropriate methodology to monitor soil organic carbon (SOC) in croplands: aligning methods with evolving monitoring reporting verification (MRV) frameworks

Ainhoa Ihasusta^a

^aUniv Toulouse, INRAE/CNRS/CNES/IRD, CESBIO, Toulouse, France; ^bISRIC – World Soil Information, Wageningen, The Netherlands; ^cCIRAD, UPR AIDA, Montpellier, France; ^dAIDA, Univ Montpellier, CIRAD, Montpellier, France; ^ePlant Production Sciences and Technology, University of Zimbabwe, Harare, Zimbabwe; ^fCSIRO Agriculture and Food, Ngunnawal Country, Black Mountain, ACT, Australia; ^gLaboratoire de Géologie, École Normale Supérieure, CNRS, Université PSL, IPSL, Paris, France; ^hINRAE, France

ABSTRACT

Monitoring soil organic carbon (SOC) has gained significant recognition, not only for national greenhouse gas inventories but also for voluntary carbon markets and agri-environmental policies. This has amplified the need for accurate, continuous, and cost-effective SOC stock monitoring from field to national scales. Consequently, methodological frameworks have emerged to address these diverse needs. They rely on measurement and/or modeling of the SOC, considering several complexities (Tiers 1, 2 and 3), combined or not with remote sensing. However, practical implementation guidelines for choosing the most suitable monitoring approach for specific contexts and purposes remain incomplete. Therefore, this study analyses current SOC monitoring methodologies for croplands and proposes a decision tree to help MRV stakeholders select the monitoring strategy considered most appropriate for their context. It confirmed that currently there are no fit-for-all-purposes method, while it recommends whenever possible, the use of measure–remeasure or parsimonious Tier 3 modeling approaches with Earth-Observation data assimilation. Indeed, the assimilation of biomass or proxies derived from remote sensing into those models allows better quantification of biomass restitution to the soil and improves model accuracy and scalability at low cost. Finally, we highlight possible improvements in the different monitoring approaches and key challenges that still need to be overcome.

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Introduction

Over the last 8000 years of agriculture, cultivated soils have lost around 116 Gt C (~510–550 Gt CO₂) [1] which had a significant impact on the atmospheric concentrations of CO₂ and CH₄ [2]. Yet, it is known that better agricultural management practices can shift the trend and increase carbon storage in agricultural soils [3,4].

Accordingly, maintaining and increasing soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks in croplands through better management practices has gained increasing attention in the global agenda (for climate change mitigation, soil health, biodiversity preservation and food security), national and international policies and carbon credit mechanisms. Monitoring SOC stock changes has become crucial not only for Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) but also for other application contexts, such as Agricultural and Environmental Policies (AEPs) and Voluntary Carbon Markets (VCMs).

Because of the diversity of contexts of monitoring and their purposes, different protocols have emerged for SOC monitoring at the national and international levels, while the one proposed by the IPCC [5,6] remains the reference for NDCs. Within the VCM, the diversity of projects is large, creating a “jungle” of SOC certification

CONTACT Ainhoa Ihasusta Univ Toulouse, INRAE/CNRS/CNES/IRD, CESBIO, Toulouse, France

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schemes and standards [7], such as VERRA VM0042 [8], Gold Standard [9], or the Low Carbon Label [10] in France. This diversity can create confusion, which reduces adoption rates, engagement and credibility.

International initiatives, including the International Research Consortium on Soil Carbon, the 4 per 1000 Initiative, the FAO Global Soil Partnership, and the European Soil Observatory, underscore the global commitment for improving SOC monitoring frameworks. These efforts aim to harmonize methodologies, develop open-access soil data platforms, and provide policymakers with reliable indicators for tracking soil health and carbon sequestration achievements and potential. Batjes et al. [11] proposed a harmonized and modular multiccosystem framework for assessing SOC stock changes, including key elements required for monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV), based on an extensive review. The monitoring component appeared to be the main challenge in developing a unified, operational MRV system. The review showed that monitoring methodologies can be organized into two main categories: those based on soil measurements (i.e. measure–remeasure) or modeling. Within the latter category, three modeling approaches are available with increasing complexity as defined by the IPCC (Tier 1, Tier 2 and Tier 3). Tier 1 and Tier 2 rely on simple equations to estimate SOC stocks and C fluxes (Equations 2.4 and 2.5 in [5]), respectively, on global or regional emission factors, whereas Tier 3 relies on process-based models using highly disaggregated data allowing to consider SOC stock variability in both space (e.g. field scale) and time due to management practices or local pedoclimatic conditions. These approaches can rely on different sources of data, from *in situ* to remote sensing, different methods, data-driven to process-based models, inducing different cost-accuracy, resolution and spatial extent profiles.

This study is built upon the MRV methodological framework proposed in Batjes et al. [11] (Figure 1). While their framework describes the conceptual workflow required to address monitoring, reporting and verification for multi-ecosystems, we focus specifically on the monitoring methods (turquoise box in Figure 1). We analyzed the workflow and interaction between building blocks for monitoring and the monitoring methods themselves, which aim to quantify SOC stock changes induced by management

Figure 1. Schematic representation of a harmonized methodological framework for MRV of SOC stock for cropland (abbreviations: FMIS, Farm Management Information system). Adapted from [11].

practices, restricting our analysis to annual cropping systems. As such, agroforestry systems and grasslands are beyond the scope of this paper. Further, it is recognized that some management practices (e.g. organic manure application or cover crops) affect not only SOC stocks [12] but also net GHG emissions [13–18]. However, in view of the overall complexity, this study focuses on SOC stock changes in croplands.

Practical implementation guidelines for monitoring SOC stock changes remain incomplete, especially for Tier 3 approaches, as these approaches lack clarity concerning inputs, including remote sensing data, model types, uncertainty assessment and spatial resolution regarding the purpose and local context of application.

In this study, to address this gap, we first present a review of the different contexts of application of SOC stock monitoring in croplands. In a second step, we analyze current SOC monitoring methodologies for croplands, from Measure/Remeasure and Tier 1 to Tier 3, with respect to the different application context requirements. We assess the current methods not only based on their scientific robustness but also considering their cost accuracy, scalability, and ease of implementation to ensure both reliability and adoption of the system. Moreover, we clarify the use, benefits and limitations of Earth observation (EO) data and assimilation schemes in an MRV framework (Figure 1). Data-driven techniques based on statistical methods and machine learning for prediction are mentioned through the description of the monitoring approaches, as these can be used for several purposes and components of an MRV framework. However, we do not consider data-driven methods as a stand-alone approach to quantify SOC stock changes in croplands. To avoid any confusion, here, we use the term “data-driven” to cover all methods that estimate relationships directly from data rather than from explicit, interpretable, process-based equations representing interactions between biophysical variables.

Further, considering that no single approach is appropriate for all contexts of application, we propose a decision tree as guidance to select the most appropriate approach for a given context. Our decision tree is inspired by the NDC IPCC [5] decision tree and adapted to the different contexts of application (AEPs, VCM).

Finally, based on the requirements of the different contexts of application and the analysis of the different methods, we identified key criteria required to align monitoring approaches with current needs and essential adaptations for the future regarding the methodologies themselves and their evaluation.

Contexts of application for SOC stock monitoring and their requirements

Voluntary carbon market (VCM): According to the 2023 *United Nations Development Programme* (UNDP) [19] High Integrity Carbon Markets Initiative report, the voluntary market refers to the issuance, purchase and sale of carbon credits on a voluntary basis, involving the financing of mitigation actions in companies' value chain (insetting) or outside their value chain (offsetting). The spatial scales of projects are variable, ranging from the field level to thousands of aggregated set of fields [20]. Insetting programs can be implemented through short-term (yearly) or pluriannual contracts where companies incentivize farmers to adopt specific carbon farming practices (e.g. cover crops). Offsetting projects last at least five years, but some schemes, such as the Australian government SOC method [21], require an assurance period of 25 years or 100 years. In this context, monitoring requires capturing the impact of management actions accurately at the field scale, as is done with Tier 3 approaches. Governance efforts are emerging at the international and regional levels for VCM regulation (e.g. the European Union (EU) published the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation (EU/2024/3012) [22]).

Agricultural and Environmental Policies (AEPs): AEPs can support SOC sequestration by incentivizing carbon farming practices, though regulation and implementation largely depend on the local context across the world. Monitoring for AEPs will likely be at the field or farm level, with short-term contracts, to reflect farmers' practices. In the US, government programs [23] promote sustainable practices compatible with SOC sequestration by incentivizing farmers by direct payments or cost sharing [24]. In Europe, incentives are provided by the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) to improve farming practices and safeguard the environment. Recently, the European Parliament adopted the EU Soil Monitoring Law [25] proposed to protect and restore soils and ensure that they are used sustainably.

Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs): NDCs are self-defined national climate pledges under the Paris Agreement [26]. Biennial transparency reports (BTRs) of SOC-related data are required (Article 13.7b; UNFCCC 2022 [27]) to track progress between the NDCs five-year report to the UNFCCC. In practice, the frequency of actual SOC stock reporting varies among countries and is influenced by national

circumstances, methodological choices, and resource availability [28]. Currently, cropland SOC monitoring for NDCs relies on different methods, which include modeling approaches (Tier 1 to Tier 3) and soil monitoring networks [29]. At present, the majority of developing parties apply a Tier 1 approach, and only 26% apply higher Tier methods [30,31]. The major challenges identified are the lack of activity data on land management and soil-specific data [30], which is emphasized by the need to cover large national territories.

Monitoring approaches

In the following analysis, the monitoring approaches have been assessed for their scientific robustness, cost accuracy, scalability, practicality (e.g. to set a baseline) and ease of implementation to ensure both reliability and suitability for different MRV contexts of application.

Cost accuracy is a key criterion for selecting a monitoring approach (measure, or modeling approach). It can be evaluated by assessing the accuracy of the method output (closeness of the estimates to the reference value) relative to the total cost of implementation, including economic, time and logistic expenses for the method application. In an operational context such as the VCM, the accuracy of the methodology is critical to ensure credibility; specifically, the estimated increase in SOC stocks is significantly different from zero, while keeping implementation costs low to maximize the financial compensation delivered to land managers or farmers for the verified SOC stock increase. Therefore, a trade-off between methodological accuracy and economic feasibility is essential to ensure both the reliability and adoption of the system. In this study, we adopt a qualitative approach for both quantifying the accuracy and the cost of monitoring. In addition, the scalability of an approach is the ability to apply it on a large scale without impacting the accuracy of the output, which is essential in many contexts of application. It is a key factor influencing the ease of implementation of an approach, along with the expertise required to apply it, its level of complexity and the amount of data to be collected.

To assess the management-induced changes in SOC stock, setting a baseline is crucial in any MRV system, as it establishes the reference against which SOC stock changes are quantified. A baseline is a counterfactual approach that generally reflects a business-as-usual scenario concerning either management practices or mitigation action. Different baseline methods are used depending on the MRV context of the application and the selected monitoring method. Alternatively, a fact-based option is to monitor a control plot that is managed to reflect business-as-usual practices. While not relying on scenarios, this approach raises a complex dilemma between having enough plots to represent diverse conditions (e.g. soil, climate) while not adversely affecting the incomes of farmers who could have used these areas for carbon farming [32]. Additional details about setting a baseline for VCM can be found in [33]; for NDCs, see Clapp and Prag [34], OECD [35] or all context of applications in [36].

Measure–remeasure

The “measure–remeasure” approach relies on soil sampling at the start and end of an MRV project. Further, depending on MRV project schemes, soil campaigns may be mandatory for modeling approach verification. *Sampling design and protocols*

For measure–remeasure, an unbiased estimate of the mean SOC stock change between the start and end dates of a project, together with an associated uncertainty, is required in a given project area (e.g. a field, farm, region or country). These requirements favor the use of probability sampling designs because of their ability to estimate unbiased means and uncertainty statistics, including confidence intervals [37–39]. This is not possible or much more difficult with purposive or model-based sampling designs. The width of a confidence interval decreases with sample size (i.e. the number of soil samples taken), which provides a means to calculate the minimum sample size needed to reach the required precision. The most basic probability sampling design is simple random sampling, but more advanced designs can also be used, such as stratified random sampling and cluster random sampling (e.g. [37]).

An important sampling design decision in measure–remeasure is whether a static or synchronous sampling design is used. In static designs, the locations visited during the measurement phase are revisited in the remeasure phase. In synchronous designs, they are not, although the strata used in the sampling design remain the same, allowing for unbiased estimates of the mean SOC stock (change) per stratum. The

advantage of static designs is that with the same sample size, a more accurate estimate of the SOC stock change is obtained, and recalculation of measurement locations is not needed between campaigns. But the disadvantage is that the design is vulnerable to fraud [40], since a project owner might put more effort in increasing the SOC stock at locations that were sampled during the measurement phase, expecting higher carbon credit profits. Therefore, for VCM purposes, a synchronous design increases credibility, but a larger number of soil samples may be needed to obtain accurate estimates when SOC stock changes are spatially highly heterogeneous [41]. For NDCs, revisiting the same locations is advisable, although it might be challenging because land use changes over time, which can mean that the location falls into a different (land use) stratum [42,43].

A strict and transparent protocol should be used to standardize field sampling and lab analysis, involving clear recommendations on the physical soil sample collection or sampling protocol, including spatial support, number of subsamples taken per short-distance composite and how, sampling depth, registered environmental variables, etc., and the laboratory methods, quality control, required lab certification, data storage, uncertainty assessment, etc. Many continental (LUCAS, [44,45]) or national [42] soil monitoring systems that are also used for NDC purposes have their own sampling protocols and set of standardized laboratory methods. These monitoring systems have been designed for various purposes, leading to significant diversity in sampling designs, protocols, sampling depths, laboratory methods, and ancillary data collection [46–48]. Note that most soil monitoring networks (e.g. LUCAS) do not collect activity data or data on carbon inputs from biomass, meaning that the causes of the SOC stock trends observed at specific points are unknown. Also, the differences in sampling support and sampling depth can be challenging for MRV in the NDC context, as they may require a transformation to align with continental or IPCC sampling default depths of 0–30 cm. An effort to derive transfer functions to account for differences in sampling and laboratory protocols between 17 European countries and the LUCAS is ongoing [49]. For now, VCM schemes often have their own prescribed sampling protocols for SOC (e.g. VERRA042) but can also follow other protocols (e.g. IPCC, ICP Forests, LUCAS, FAO-GSP [50,51]).

It should be mentioned that digital soil mapping and pedometrics provide various data-driven methods to derive maps of SOC stock changes between two points in time, as well as predictions of the total SOC stock change for an area. Many of these methods make use of machine learning and geostatistics and have an important advantage over other methods in that they also quantify the prediction accuracy. Notable examples of such analyses are [52–54]. Uncertainty quantification is important because it enables deriving prediction intervals and applying statistical significance testing. In this way, these model-based approaches can also calculate the minimum number of SOC stock observations required to reach a desired accuracy level, similar to what design-based sampling theory can do as described above.

Soil sample analysis

The soil samples should be prepared and analyzed using a reliable, reproducible method with quantified accuracy, whether in the field or in the laboratory. SOC stocks are derived from measurements of the SOC concentration, bulk density of fine-Earth (<2 mm), gravel content (>2 mm) and sampling thickness (e.g. 0–30 cm or 0–100 cm). Bulk density changes over time [55] due to physical factors (e.g. water content, freezing, rainfall intensity, drought, and runoff) and the adoption of C farming practices (e.g. cover crops, tillage, and no-tillage). For example, in swelling soils, the bulk density can increase from 1.34 Mg m^{-3} at saturation to 1.52 Mg m^{-3} when completely dry [56]. Additionally, conservation conventional, nil and chisel tillage practices can result in different bulk densities on the same soil type. For instance in [57], different tillage practices led to significant differences after 10 years in topsoil (0–10 cm) bulk densities (1.39, 1.37, and 1.30 Mg m^{-3}) compared to the starting bulk density (1.33 Mg m^{-3}). Therefore, high-quality bulk density measurements are crucial in addition to the SOC concentration at each sampling time point to accurately assess SOC stock changes. The use of the equivalent soil mass approach is recommended [58–60].

Field methods, such as field spectrometry using Vis-NIR [61,62], are faster and less expensive than lab analyses, but often have a lower accuracy. Lab analysis should be conducted by a certified laboratory following ISO¹ or GLOSOLAN² standard operating procedures to ensure comparability, credibility and quality. Indeed, changes in laboratory procedures can be an important source of uncertainty, especially for long-term experiments [63]. For SOC stock change estimation, the uncertainty and the lower limit of detection of a lab method should be lower than the expected ΔSOC . This is difficult to achieve because the nominal expected change in ΔSOC over 5 years is less than 2% [64]. Even et al. [65] reported errors of 250% when multiple lab analysis methods, sample preparation techniques, and operators are considered.

Costs and accuracy

The accuracy of the resulting data, which is restricted by the lower limit of detection of the analysis, depends on a chosen trade-off between the sampling costs and the number of soil samples. The selection of the number of soil samples should consider the spatial variation of the SOC stock [66] and the laboratory analysis uncertainty. The sampling costs include the cost for calculating the sampling design, for taking the physical soil samples (travel costs, instruments, staff salary) and the cost per sample for lab analysis, including shipment of samples to the lab. All the mentioned costs differ per country and per soil property. One way to reduce operational and lab costs is to take composite soil samples per subfield area, field, farm, stratum or project instead of the short distance composite point samples that are common practice in NDCs [67–69]. For instance, Deluz et al. [70] found that for their context, 20 soil subsamples per field collected in an X shape were required to observe a statistically significant change in the SOC content (g g^{-1}) at the field scale after at least 5 years, with a minimum detectable change of 0.1% in the SOC content. It should be noted that at least 2 samples are needed to derive the uncertainty associated with the estimate, and choosing a large spatial support for composite samples may equal out the SOC stock (change) due to heterogeneity, e.g. as a result of different soil properties or management.

The number of subsamples and the sampling support should be determined statistically based on the SOC stock (change) variability of the targeted area, which is done in most MRV protocols through preliminary sampling [71]. A sampling design incorporating indices derived from remote sensing is also emerging to reduce sample sizes [72,73].

Finally, cost–accuracy curves depict the relationship between cost and sample size and the relationship between sample size and accuracy. They can be useful tools in determining the balance or trade-off between cost and accuracy. The cost–accuracy relation depends on various local or regional factors; hence, it is case dependent and should be estimated at the local or regional level [74,75].

Application for MRV contexts

Bradford et al. [76] concluded that monitoring SOC stock changes at the individual field scale with a measure–remeasure approach is not practically feasible when point or short-distance soil sampling is applied because without abundant soil sampling estimates are inaccurate due to within-field variability in SOC stocks. However, they demonstrated that accurate and robust estimates are achievable at the project scale (multifield level) because, in such cases, more soil samples can be taken. In their case study, they reported that to estimate the causal effect of management on the SOC stock change of $+3 \text{ MgC ha}^{-1}$ over a 10-year period in a statistically significant way, at least 650 samples were required for 30 pairs of fields (30 control plots and 30 treatment fields). In addition, Potash et al. [32] further confirmed that the measure–remeasure approach is not economically feasible for small projects (<5000 fields) under 5 years to remeasurement. This suggests that measure–remeasure is not adequate for VCM-insetting projects or for AEPs contexts that are either short-term projects (<5 years) or require SOC change quantification at the field or farm level. However, measure–remeasure becomes financially more advantageous for VCM offsetting projects, including a large number of fields, especially with increasing time (~10 years) to remeasurement, demonstrating economies of spatial and temporal scale [32].

Setting a baseline

The monitoring part of the MRV scheme has to estimate the SOC stock change that is the consequence of the new management practices and distinguish it from the SOC stock trend without the implementation of carbon farming practices (which may be induced by climate or spatial variation effects). However, the difference between two SOC measurements over time is the result of the combination of these effects; therefore, the baseline design must consider this issue. For now, two different types of baselines are implemented according to the project scheme [33]: either a static or a dynamic baseline. With a static baseline approach, the SOC can be measured before practice implementation and then assessed under a measure–remeasure framework, where SOC stocks are periodically measured and credits are issued based on the change in the SOC over time. This implies that a correction should be applied to carbon credits to distinguish the business-as-usual trend from the variations induced by new management practices targeted for MRV contexts. Indeed, the SOC steady-state assumption between the two measurement times is usually an unrealistic baseline. For instance, the Australia Soil Carbon 2021 method [21,77] uses a static baseline approach and applies a series of conservative discounts that include permanence discounts, adjustments for within-stratum variability and temporarily withheld credits if only two sampling rounds (including the

baseline) have been used for reporting. In this static baseline approach, the lack of consideration of dynamic effects (e.g. meteorological effects or extreme climatic events) in the correction to fully assess the SOC stock changes due to new management practices is still questioned [78,79].

On the other hand, the dynamic baseline is based on a counterfactual approach, which requires the monitoring of control plots reflecting the effect of business-as-usual management practices (i.e. the SOC stock changes trend without the implementation of carbon farming practices). Therefore, the carbon credit resulting from the implementation of carbon farming practices is the difference between the SOC stock changes measured in the treatment fields (where new management practices have been applied) and the one measured in the control plots. Despite the advantage of distinguishing the effects of management practices on SOC stock changes, this approach can be more costly, as it relies on twice as many measurements, and the control plots may not be completely representative of the treatment fields in terms of soil properties or microclimate. This, as stated earlier, raises a trade-off between having enough control plots for representativeness and economic impacts for farmers [32].

Tier 1 and Tier 2 approaches

The 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories [5] defined different approaches (Tiers) for carrying out GHG inventories. Each Tier represents a level of increasing methodological complexity. Depending on the context of the application and the availability/accuracy of input data, the appropriate or feasible Tier level should be chosen [11,36].

Tier 1 is the basic method in which the SOC stock change calculation can be done using simple equations such as the “gain loss” or “stock difference” method (see equations 2.4 and 2.5 in [5] Chapter 2 and in Volume 4 of [80]), where emissions are estimated using average emission/stock change factors for large eco-regions of the world, using globally available data and default equations [5,6]. It requires data such as areas for different land use classes, climates, soil types, land use changes (initial and final), land management and inputs to the soil. Major climate zone delineations and decision trees for soil categories are provided by the IPCC (in [6] Chapter 3 and in Volume 4 of [81]). Then, diverse sources can be used for the remaining information, including regional to national statistics, field-level data or products derived from remote sensing [31].

Tier 2 is of intermediate complexity and uses the same equations as Tier 1. However, it allows an inventory to incorporate country-specific data (e.g [82–85]). Therefore, it is considered good practice for countries to use a Tier 2 method when possible [86], even if they are only able to better specify certain components of the Tier 1 method [87].

In practice, many countries, including those in western Europe, still use a Tier 1 approach for their national GHG reporting [29]. However, the “2023 revised LULUCF regulation” [<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/839/oj>] requires that from 2026 onwards, reporting be done using a Tier 2 approach and then later, Tier 3 methods (see below) for a subset of land, including among others, forests and peatlands that undergo restoration or protection for nature directives [88]. The latter requirement is particularly challenging for SOC, for which Tier 1 is still used by many EU Member States for several land categories.

Several studies (e.g [89–91]) showed that the conceptual limitations of the Tier 1 default calculation method can be addressed by introducing a simple “steady-state” modeling component. For cropland, for example, the “IPCC 2019 Refinements” [92] present a simplified process-based method that relies on the C pools steady-state solution of the Century model [93]. Similarly, Villarino et al. [83,94] proposed an adapted Tier 2 approach in which the RothC model [95] was used to determine region-specific SOC change factors and reference SOC levels under native vegetation for the Argentinean Pampa region. Alternatively, for Australia, CSIRO implemented a steady-state Tier 2 methodology with a spatially-explicit modeling component based on the FullCAM tool [96]. Karstens et al. [97] used the CENTURY model [93] for Tier 2 level calculations as applied to global croplands. Although this improved Tier 2 method uses process-based models, it cannot be considered a Tier 3 level, as in this context, models are used in a simpler way (~20 parameters compared to >100 parameters in Tier 3 models). It is used either to derive annual SOC stock changes from the current SOC stock to the future steady-state SOC stock [92] or to derive region-specific emission factors [83,94], which are required in Tier 1 and Tier 2 IPCC equations [5,6]. This improved Tier 2 method cannot simulate SOC stock dynamics induced by local management practices and environmental variation over time.

Tier 3 approach: process-based modeling

According to the IPCC [92] a Tier 3 approach uses a highly disaggregated Tier 2 approach or a country-specific method based on process modeling and/or detailed measurement. Tier 3 approaches are recommended by the IPCC when and where possible, as they are considered to be more accurate than lower Tiers are, although Tier 3 approaches are the most demanding in terms of complexity and data requirements. These methods are based on various types of modeling and input data from different sources and can rely on measurements for verification. In this section, we first present the general inputs required to run the models, then, we describe Earth observation (EO) data and how to integrate them into modeling approaches, and finally, we describe and assess Tier 3 modeling approaches.

Input datasets

Soil properties

Process-based models require information on the physical and chemical properties of the soil as inputs, for example texture (clay, sand, and silt contents), gravel content, bulk density, pH, CaCO₃ content and C/N ratio. While global and continental digital soil maps (DSMs), such as SoilGrids [98], GSM [99] and LUCAS [67], offer broad coverage at a fairly fine resolution; inherently, they are not meant for applications at the field scale [98], hence not suited for carbon farming [100,101]. Yogo et al. [102] for example, showed that (mis)using such global products for fine-scale applications leads to large uncertainties of the soil parameters (SOC, clay, CaCO₃, pH and C/N) (RRMSE = 19–118%, median = 46%) Compared to using field measurements. County-level medians from the French BDAT database [103] can reduce this error (RRMSE = 7–26%, median = 18%), though adjustments may be needed in calcareous soils. Ultimately, direct field sampling remains the most accurate approach, with uncertainties in the analyzed soil samples, which are typically less than 10% (e.g. coefficient of variation = 4.3% between replicates of the same trial for the SOC stock in [104]). However, ensuring the representativeness of these point measurements, particularly when scaling up to field or farm-level maps, remains a challenge. In this context, it is recommended that the operator starts by investigating the availability of the soil data required to implement their Tier 3 approach, first in local digital soil maps, then regional, national and finally global datasets.

Climatic forcing variables

Climatic variables are used as forcing variables in all Tier 3 modeling approaches, whether to modulate the mineralization rate of the soil compartment (e.g. temperature, precipitation, evaporation) or to simulate vegetation growth via photosynthesis (e.g. incoming and diffuse radiation) and autotrophic respiration. The spatial and temporal resolutions required depend on the selected modeling approach. Although local, regional or national networks of weather stations can provide more accurate data, global weather reanalysis products such as ERA5-Land (ECMWF), which offer a dekilometric resolution of aggregated daily information [105], are commonly used and well suited for MRV applications. Local weather stations are generally either used for calibration and validation exercises at the field scale to develop modeling approaches or combined with weather models to produce unbiased spatiotemporal data [106].

Activity data

Accurate activity data on management practices are essential for estimating SOC stock changes in croplands, especially at the field scale. Key drivers include crop type, the presence of cover crops, stubble/straw management and organic amendments [107,108]. The required level of detail regarding management varies by modeling approach, as discussed in the corresponding sections below.

Collecting reliable activity data remains challenging, especially at large scales [109,110]. Even when sourced from Farm Management Information Systems (FMIS), data must be checked and harmonized by specialists. To our knowledge, none of the current MRV schemes or tools quantify the uncertainty introduced by activity data, though this can affect SOC change estimates [111] or other agro-environmental variables [112,113], especially in applications such as carbon markets, where data quality is often lower than that in controlled experimental conditions. Therefore, we recommend assessing the uncertainty of activity data whenever possible and accounting for them in the calculation of SOC stock changes and their associated uncertainties.

Earth observation: technologies, assimilation, and limitations

The availability of free high-resolution satellite data has positioned remote sensing as an integral component of modern agricultural applications [114]. Remote sensing offers a scalable solution to provide cost-effective MRVs, especially through open-access data from missions such as Sentinel-2, Sentinel-1 or Landsat. These datasets provide frequent observations of field status, vegetation and soil conditions that impact SOC stock changes. The direct interpretation of satellite imagery requires the consideration of atmospheric effects, sensor noise, complex interactions and indirect biogeophysical relationships between electromagnetic signals and matter [115].

Biogeophysical variables

Biogeophysical variables can be obtained using empirical relationships or machine learning-based approaches [116]. A physically-based alternative is to use radiative transfer models (RTMs), which simulate how electromagnetic radiation interacts with soil, vegetation, and the atmosphere. By minimizing the difference between the RTM estimates and satellite observations, it is possible to retrieve estimates of biogeophysical parameters [117,118].

The leaf area index (LAI) and green leaf area index (GLAI) can be retrieved from visible multispectral remote sensing or proxy synthetic aperture radar (SAR) data. The most popular RTM model for LAI retrieval using visible bands is the PROSAIL model [119], or its surrogate ANN model (BVNET). Empirical approaches that link vegetation indices such as the NDVI to the LAI can also be applied [120]. Remote sensing has also been applied to retrieve aboveground biomass (AGB) based on empirical relationships between surface reflectance and biomass [121,122] or using machine learning [123,124]. Belowground biomass can be estimated from AGB using allometric functions [125]. The total carbon inputs from biomass to the soil can then be obtained, including for cover crops, which is essential considering that there are no yield data for cover crops. To improve the representation of plant stress and nutritional needs, RTM models such as PROSPECT-D can be used to retrieve chlorophyll content [126,127]. This approach is expected to become more reliable with the upcoming FLEX satellite [128].

Surface soil moisture (SSM) and soil surface roughness are also key factors influencing soil carbon decomposition. Improving water-related constraints in SOC modeling is essential for enhancing model reliability, especially under climate change, as emphasized by Bruni et al. [129]. The SSM is best retrieved using passive microwave observations at long wavelengths [130], but its coarse spatial resolution limits its field-scale application. SAR data provide finer resolution but are more sensitive to vegetation and surface roughness, often leading to biased estimates [131,132] which are reduced by fusion with visible data [133]. Soil moisture for deeper soil profiles (~30 cm) can be estimated using statistical models [134] or through assimilation [135].

The superficial SOC content can be estimated using hyperspectral and multispectral reflectance data in the visible (400–700 nm) and shortwave infrared (1000–2500 nm) bands due to organic matter absorption in these bandwidths [136,137]. Machine learning methods such as random forest (RF), multiple linear regressions (MLR), or Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are commonly used to estimate superficial SOC from remote sensing, but they are limited by many factors, including the constraint of observing bare soil conditions, increased uncertainties in high clay soils, the impact of soil moisture, the impact of crop residues, and the impact of tillage on surface reflection through soil roughness [138–140]. Moreover, the development of carbon farming practices (e.g. cover crop combined or without reduced or no tillage) will reduce the time window for observing bare soil through EO to estimate the superficial SOC content. In a recent study over extensive datasets in Germany, Broeg et al. [141] concluded that remote sensing does not allow to estimate the SOC stocks or SOC stock changes over the full soil depth. Indeed, bulk density cannot be estimated by remote sensing, and SOC stocks are highly variable with depth [142]. As a result, superficial SOC mapping via remote sensing finds its most relevant application in DSM approaches for optimal sampling. In addition, a wide range of products can be derived from remote sensing to improve DSM, from land cover maps and climate-related time series to vegetation and surface property indices. According to their nature, they are either used as static or dynamic covariates to enhance the estimation of the spatial and temporal variation in the SOC stock. Many recent DSM studies have combined these remote sensing-derived products with soil sample data to produce spatiotemporal evolution of the SOC stock and its uncertainty, with a resolution ranging from 25 m to 100 m [143–147]. While these methods succeed to predict statistically significant spatial patterns of SOC, temporal variation is more challenging [144–146] because of the small rate of SOC change compared to spatial variability and the difficulty to quantify this subtle dynamic variation with reliable uncertainty quantification at the point level. To address these challenges, aggregating predictions to larger spatial support is a way to reduce prediction uncertainty [52], and additional long time series of soil measurements are necessary to improve temporal variation prediction. While they might not be appropriate for

the VCM context and short-term reporting projects such as AEPs, these recent advances in DSM can be relevant for NDCs [145,147].

Key agricultural practices can also be retrieved from EO data through indices or RTMs. The most mature application is “landcover land use” mapping for crops and cover crops [148,149]. Cover crop mapping is important not only because it is a major lever for C sequestration in arable lands [15,150], but also because its biomass development shows high spatiotemporal heterogeneity at both the intrafield and interfield scales [124,151,152]. This variability is explained by the fact that these crops receive less management attention than main crops, in addition to their short cycle length and mixed seeds nature, which also make their mapping challenging. Tillage and ploughing can also be detected using indices derived from multispectral or hyperspectral data [153,154] along with conservative tillage and residue cover fractions [155]. Two key management practices for SOC modeling and overall carbon budget assessment remain challenging to monitor using remote sensing: (1) straw management, specifically, whether residues are left on the soil or exported and in which proportions [156,157], and (2) the type and amount of organic amendments, although the detection of amendment application (“yes” or “no”) appears feasible [158,159].

Assimilation of biogeophysical data in modeling framework

As shown in Figure 1, Tier 3 modeling approaches are separated in function of their ability to assimilate EO data. Data assimilation consists of integrating observational data into process-based models to improve the accuracy of simulations while considering uncertainties from observations and model predictions [160,161]. Assimilation schemes may integrate the output geophysical variable from the RTM retrievals or include the RTM model as an observation module [162]. Four main families of data assimilation methods are applied in soil and crop modeling, which are often used in hybrid combinations: sequential methods such as the Ensemble Kalman Filter [120,163,164], variational methods such as the 4DVAR [165,166], calibration methods such as the simplex algorithm [167–169], and probabilistic methods such as Bayesian inference [170,171]. The most common application for EO is the use of LAI time series assimilation in crop or ecosystem models [160,168]. Using a high temporal and spatial resolution series of LAI allows the model to estimate the spatial heterogeneity of biomass production and its associated carbon inputs to the soil [172]. It implicitly accounts for a range of effects and events impacting biomass production that are difficult to parameterize in crop models, such as water stress, nitrogen stress, presence of pests, diseases [173], extreme climatic events and the impact of spontaneous regrowth, weeds and cover crops [168,174,175].

Limitations and recommendation on Earth-Observation data and assimilation

Earth Observation data are not universally applicable, as this depends on the compatibility between the satellite sensor and the characteristics of the observed field or practices. This creates limitations that underscore the need for context-specific monitoring and emphasize the importance of integrating multiple sensor data. Another critical issue is the continuity of free EO missions, which currently depend on institutional programs such as the EU's Copernicus and NASA's satellite fleets. Each EO technology comes with its own set of limitations:

- (i) Optical sensors are sensitive to cloud cover, cloud shadows, and terrain effects in mountainous regions. They also suffer from reflectance saturation and can be influenced by field borders and vegetation structures such as hedgerows.
- (ii) SAR sensors are affected by radio frequency interference (RFI), intense rainfall, complex terrain, and challenges in interpreting signals in heterogeneous environments.
- (iii) Passive microwave sensors are limited mainly by coarse spatial resolution and vulnerability to RFI.
- (iv) Thermal sensors face challenges related to observation frequency, the influence of water vapor, and constraints in tropical regions.

The assimilation algorithms also face challenges. In the context of SOC monitoring, where crop cycles should be considered over long-time windows in order to quantify crop biomass and carbon inputs to the soil and where the system is impacted by point events (presence of pests, extreme events), the application of variational methods [165,166] presents a challenge. Sequential assimilations (recursive) such as Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) [176] present advantages for real-time applications for irrigation and fertilizer needs [120,163,164], but over time, the predicted model ensembles may diverge and stop being representative of reality over the course of the cycles. Iterative calibration or probabilistic methods [167–170,177] are efficient

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the soil-centered modeling approach. The input data sources are classified according to their accuracy, with red being the lowest and green the highest. In addition, the cost arrows represent the cost of collecting these data, with red being the highest cost and green being the lowest cost.

but very computationally expensive at a large scale. Thus, noniterative probabilistic approaches such as Bayesian inference [172] have emerged as very promising framework combining long-time scale prediction and uncertainty estimates. However, it is recommended to use assimilation algorithms in conjunction with parsimonious models, which aim to reproduce observed system behavior with the simplest possible structure and fewest parameters, ensuring parameter identifiability, model transparency, and robustness [178]. For instance, Dumont et al. [170] highlight the challenges of parameter identifiability in models that rely on many parameters, such as the STICS model (>200 parameters), where moderate to strong correlations persist between parameters even after a drastic restriction to 9 parameters for the optimization process, leading to parameter compensation. These interdependencies suggest that the assimilated observation data were probably not sufficient to accurately estimate all nine selected parameters. In contrast, using a more parsimonious crop model, such as SAFYE-CO₂ (~44 parameters), Wijmer et al. [172] improves carbon fluxes and biomass estimation at the intrafield level over a large region by optimizing 7 independent parameters via a Bayesian approach. The use of a parsimonious model in conjunction with their assimilation methods allow to reduce computational time and assimilates more data, such as high-resolution (temporal and spatial) EO data, which enhance parameter estimation. Finally, the uneven spatial and temporal distribution of EO data pose an equity challenge because the uncertainty of the assimilation decreases with increasing number of observations. This creates a disparity between regions, potentially adversely affecting farmers in areas with less EO coverage.

Description and assessment of the Tier 3 modeling approaches

Various process-based modeling approaches are available to estimate changes in SOC stocks, each with distinct characteristics. In this review, we propose a classification of these modeling approaches based on three key criteria: (i) compartments they simulate, whether soil-centered or full ecosystem models; (ii) within ecosystem models, the degree of coupling between soil and vegetation processes; and (iii) the integration of EO data through data assimilation techniques (Figures 2 and 3).

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the ecosystem modeling approach with or without EO assimilation (in dashed lines), either using parsimonious models with a light coupling strategy between soil and vegetation (in violet) or “off-the-shelf” models using a strong coupling strategy between soil and vegetation (in orange). The input data sources are classified according to their accuracy, with red being the lowest and green the highest. In addition, the cost arrows represent the cost of collecting these data, with red representing the highest cost and green representing the lowest cost.

All these approaches generate business-as-usual scenarios for baseline definition, which enables the consideration of the ongoing SOC stock change trend prior to the implementation of mitigation activities in the project.

In process-based models, two main strategies can be identified for representing SOC dynamics. The first one divides SOC into several conceptual pools of carbon, classified by their differing turnover times, where their dynamics follow a first-order decay rate (e.g. AMG [104], RothC [179], ICBM [180], Century [181], DayCent [182], Yasso7 [183]). As these pools are conceptual and not measurable, these models require initialization methods that are described in the next section.

The second strategy for SOC modeling is based on measurable pools (typically particulate and mineral-associated organic matter: POM and MAOM) and includes an explicit microbial carbon pool, with a deterministic representation of SOM dynamics through biological, chemical, and physical mechanisms. Examples include MIMICS [184], Millennial [185] and MEMS2 [186]. These process-rich models have a cost, involving numerous equations at daily time steps and parameters to calibrate [187]. The limited availability of observational data is a critical limitation for calibration and further development [186,188,189] and an issue for initialization, which is commonly addressed by performing spin-up for C pool initialization [184,186–189]. Furthermore, Shi et al. [190] has shown that complex model structures (e.g. CLM4.5, MIMICS) can amplify uncertainty in SOC projection compared with conventional first order decay models like Century.

While they are essential for enhancing the understanding of soil processes from a research perspective, they are yet to be validated against diachronic measurements of SOC evolutions [184–186,189,191,192]. The implementation of these methods for operational MRV initiatives seems to be challenging because of the high data demands, complex validation process, and high uncertainties associated with their predictions,

rendering them too complex and expensive (e.g. microbial and SOC fraction initialization, uncertainty assessment in high-dimensional systems, etc.).

Therefore, we consider only conceptual C pools models with an SOC dynamic following a first-order decay rate when recommending modeling approaches for SOC monitoring.

Initializing SOC stock and C pools

The initialization of SOC stocks and pool distributions is a critical step for all Tier 3 models with conceptual C pools, influencing their accuracy. Depending on the model's structure (e.g. number and nature of pools), various methods can be applied, with varying trade-offs between cost and accuracy. The spin-up method is widely applied because it requires no additional soil observations [193,194]. However, it relies on uncertain input data (climate, land use, and carbon inputs) and assumes unrealistic steady-state conditions, especially in dynamic systems such as carbon farming or recently converted fields [195,196]. In some models, such as AMG [104,197], default values can be used to initialize pools distribution based on the long-term history of the field (cropland or grassland), but their accuracy is limited in dynamic environments with recent land-use transitions.

More advanced approaches align measured SOC fractions with conceptual model pools, as shown for the soil model RothC [198–200] or the ecosystem model DAYCENT [201], although improving the accuracy generally requires modifying the decomposition rate of SOC kinetic pools [199,202]. On the other hand, the combination of RockEval® thermal stability analysis results and a learning model calibrated on LTE data (PARTYsoc; [195,203,204]) allows to initialize the C pools in AMG and repeatedly demonstrates better accuracy in simulations without modifying the model. While increasing the cost of MRV, these methods can improve model accuracy and be implemented on soil monitoring networks to explore their potential before more complex models are used, as suggested in Kanari et al. [195].

When estimating absolute SOC stocks, high-accuracy methods such as RockEval® [205] or SOC fractionation should be prioritized, especially in dynamic systems. Conversely, when the aim is to assess SOC stock changes (Δ SOCs) between scenarios (e.g. baseline vs. carbon farming), this category of first-order kinetic soil models is generally less sensitive to the initial pool distribution as long as the same initial conditions are used for all scenarios [102,206] and can be the case for more complex models such as Ecosys [207]. The requirements of the verification scheme must also be considered, since the Δ SOCs between management scenarios cannot be directly evaluated through soil measurements, except if a control plot with a business-as-usual scenario is used as a reference. For large-scale applications, such as NDC reporting, cost-effective approaches for initializing SOC pools using proximal sensing, as demonstrated in Australia's FullCAM framework [96,208,209], may provide scalable solutions for SOC stock changes accounting at regional and national levels of MRV for croplands.

Soil-centered modeling approach. The soil-centered approach (see Figure 2), the simplest Tier 3 method presented here, is based on a soil model that considers the impacts of climate, soil type, and carbon inputs (e.g. crop residues, cover crops, organic amendments) on SOC stock changes (e.g. AMG [104], RothC [179], ICBM [180], Century [181], Yasso7 [183,210]). The timesteps of soil models generally range from monthly to annual. To run the model, this approach requires weather data, soil property data, a few activity data (mainly on organic amendments and straw management), and to calculate carbon inputs to the soil from the biomass, crop species, yield and cover crop biomass estimates are needed. Depending on the complexity of the model, it can also consider the impact of additional management practices other than those directly impacting the C inputs to the soil (e.g. tillage, mineral fertilization), leading to additional activity data being required.

Carbon inputs estimation for soil models

Soil models do not simulate vegetation growth; hence, C inputs to the soil from biomass have to be estimated elsewhere. Carbon input estimation methods have a significant impact on the uncertainty of SOC estimation [211,212], even if the choice of the soil model has a greater impact [212]. That is why, selecting an appropriate soil model adapted to the local pedoclimatic context and management practices, i.e. validated properly under these conditions [191,192] and an accurate method to estimate biomass and carbon inputs from biomass to the soil, are crucial. In VCM and AEPs MRV contexts, field-specific biomass inputs to the soil are needed to reflect the variation induced by farmer management practices (e.g. fertilization, irrigation) and the environment (e.g. soil properties, topography, microclimate of the field)

while biomass regional statistics can be used in NDCs context. Of course, if collecting field-specific data to estimate carbon inputs is more accurate than regional statistics, it is also more costly, as shown in [Figure 2](#), except for methods based on EO to estimate crop or cover crop biomass.

Often, with this approach, yield data are combined with allometric coefficients (e.g. [125]) to estimate carbon inputs, as is done in the French low-carbon label method. However, yield information often relies on average field or farm-scale yields, neglecting spatial variability, while yield maps from sensor-equipped harvesters are prone to uncertainties [213,214]. Additionally, carbon input estimates based on yield depend on the harvest index (HI), which varies by species, variety, and management, leading to significant uncertainty [215].

Alternative methods can be considered, such as *in situ* biomass sampling or plant/ecosystem models to estimate biomass production or yield (e.g. SIMPLE [216], SAFY(E-CO₂) [168,174,175,217], and STICS [218]). However, *in situ* destructive biomass measurements are not scalable because of their cost and lack of representation of the average field without a proper sampling strategy (e.g. stratified sampling based on vegetation indices). Further, plant models require extensive data about practice management according to their complexity and cannot provide reliable estimates unless constrained by observations (e.g. EO) (see [section 2.3.3.2. Ecosystem modeling approach](#)).

As explained in the previous section, the aboveground biomass of crops and cover crops can be retrieved from remote sensing observations at high resolution, which enables the consideration of the spatial variability of biomass production and then carbon inputs to the soil, which is crucial in an overall C sequestration quantification strategy. Indeed, the intra- and interfield heterogeneity of cover crop biomass is usually greater than that of main crops [124,151,152], which is not well represented in average regional statistics. For instance, the French agricultural cooperative Agrod'Oc measured the dry aboveground biomass of cover crops (mainly faba beans) ranging from 0.9 to over 9 t ha⁻¹ (with a mean of 3.98 t ha⁻¹) in southwestern France (covering ~150 km) (pers. comm.). Note that EO-based biomass estimates can be produced at a large scale and at once, leading to a high cost–accuracy ratio (see [Figure 2](#)).

The cost of monitoring depends mainly on the cost for collecting data. This cost usually increases along with the source of data, which provides higher accuracy except for the cover crop aboveground biomass when estimated by remote sensing (see arrows representing the cost and accuracy of the data in [Figure 2](#)). *Validation of soil-centered approach and their uncertainty*

The soil-centered approach can be validated only with *in situ* measurements of SOC stock changes, SOC fraction changes or with soil respiration measurements (e.g. using automatic or portable soil respiration chambers), as other carbon budget components are not simulated (e.g. biomass, CO₂ fluxes). Uncertainty assessment is not included as part of soil models, which require external analysis through analytical methods [219] or numerical methods such as Monte Carlo [220,221]. However, including systematic uncertainty assessment in the approach is crucial for MRV monitoring tools to improve their credibility.

Ecosystem modeling approach. The ecosystem modeling approach relies on process-oriented models, which simulate mechanistically the plant and soil processes and climate interactions with various levels of complexity. Additionally, the effects of climate, soil, and management practices are accounted for in the modeling of the different compartments and cycles.

Key components of the carbon budget are estimated, such as biomass production, and for some models, CO₂ fluxes, which enables to evaluate the model against various independent datasets (e.g. CO₂ fluxes at flux tower sites, annual carbon budget, biomass, yield, as in [168] at finer timescales (e.g. half-hourly, daily) and not only against SOC stock changes measurements, which are typically repeated every ~5 years. An overview of the carbon budget components of the field at different spatial and temporal scales can overcome the issue of representativeness of soil samples in space and time for model validation, as underscored by Guan et al. [222].

Two modeling strategies are observed for SOC monitoring (see [Figure 3](#)): (i) The first relies on existing, well-established “off-the-shelf” ecosystem models that simulate carbon dynamics through strong coupling and feedback mechanisms between vegetation and soil (e.g. EPIC [223], DAYCENT [182,224,225], DNDC [226], STICS [218,227], DAISY [228], DSSAT [229], SALUS [230]). We refer to these models as “off-the-shelf” since they were initially developed for agri-environmental research rather than for MRV purposes. Nevertheless, they are now viable options to monitor SOC stock changes in MRV contexts because of their ability to estimate the carbon budget or SOC stock changes. (ii) The second relies on a combination of

parsimonious plant and soil models, usually assimilating EO data, enabling a light coupling strategy between soil and vegetation where mutual feedback is minimized and the number of parameters is reduced (e.g. the plant model provides biomass inputs to the soil model). This type of approach is still under development and is well designed for MRV purposes.

Ecosystems models “off-the-shelf” without EO assimilation

“Off-the-shelf” cropland ecosystem models provide a holistic approach to plant–soil interactions and biogeochemical cycles, making them valuable for decision-making. They simulate various crops and practices as well as a range of agri-environmental variables, enabling assessments of management changes and climate impacts on production and SOC stock changes [231–238]. The spatial resolution of ecosystem models without EO assimilation is often at the best field scale. As a result, these models are able to model carbon dynamics at the field level and possibly demonstrate interfield heterogeneity. However, the spatial resolution of their application in an MRV context is usually not fine enough to identify patterns within the field and capture intrafield spatial heterogeneity, For instance in biomass development. These models require a rather high level of expertise and have often been developed, calibrated and evaluated on uniform, well-monitored field trials where detailed and accurate data on management practices, soil and weather were collected (STICS [227], EPIC [239], CERES [240], DayCent [225], DAISY [241]). Hence, despite their proven performances in agronomic and environmental studies to predict SOC stock changes under different pedo-climatic conditions and for various practices [231–238,242], these controlled conditions may not reflect the heterogeneous realities encountered on farms and can lead to significant uncertainties when such models are applied in a VCM context on farms, as highlighted by Popkin [243], even when they are applied in their domain of validity. Additionally, those models do not simulate the effects of pests, diseases and extreme climatic events on crop development and their consequences for SOC stock changes [244].

The large volume of input data required (e.g. seeding density, date and depth, irrigation dates and amount, mineral fertilization dose and date of application) and the large number of parameters to calibrate them make ecosystem model application over large areas costly and time consuming (even if activity data are collected through FMIS, as they need to be checked first for consistency, accuracy, etc.), while increasing the risk of uncertainty in the model outputs. Ensuring the reliability of model outputs becomes more difficult, especially in situations where data might be missing or uncertain [111–113], and require expertise to address assumptions and uncertainties. Like soil models, many ecosystem models do not include uncertainty assessments of the output variables and, in particular, uncertainties resulting from activity data.

With “off-the-shelf” modeling approaches, as in Ogle et al. [221], the uncertainty in SOC stock change estimates may be strongly scale-dependent (inversely). In that study, using the Century model [181,245], uncertainties reached 739%–674% at the site level and decreased to 118–114% at the regional scale. Therefore, if quantifying uncertainty in SOC stock changes at the scale of carbon farming projects is needed to increase trust in the carbon credits, this approach may lead to injustices for farmers, as its accuracy may be poor at the farm scale. Additionally Palosuo et al. [244] showed that, under limited data resource conditions and minimal calibrations (daily weather, basic soil properties, crop and soil management) reproducing large-scale application, the eight compared models show large variations between estimations of biomass and LAI. None could predict wheat yields accurately at the field scale without further calibration, although the other parameters were set based on previous study applications that were geographically and physiologically comparable. Similar conclusions were obtained with the same method for spring barley in Rötter et al. [246]. This suggests that even in their domain of validity (i.e. conditions comparable with several studies where model calibrations have been validated with independent datasets), “off-the-shelf” ecosystem models would lead to inaccurate estimation of operational conditions for MRV projects at the field scale (e.g. AEPs, VCM, especially for insetting). As these models are already used outside the domain of agro-environmental studies, notably for NDC reports [91,92], it is important to understand the divergence between models' outputs. To answer this question, Brilli et al. [247] compared nine models and analyzed their strengths and weaknesses to accurately represent SOC and GHG dynamics. It confirmed that these models' performances are most sensitive to ill-defined pedo-climatic conditions, followed by misrepresentation of the effects of management practices, and inappropriate scale application (both temporal and spatial).

This approach is also the most demanding in terms of input data, especially activity data, to accurately estimate SOC stock changes, which increases the cost of monitoring. The more accurate the data, the more costly they are. However, this approach may be relevant for the NDC context to represent annual and regional trends, as already available regional/national statistics on activity data can be used. In addition,

some of these models have already been used for national inventories, meaning that keeping this approach would allow consistency with former national reporting.

Ecosystems models “off-the-shelf” with EO assimilation

As most ecosystem models cannot capture intrafield spatial variability in plant and soil processes, one option is to assimilate high-resolution vegetation indices or plant biophysical properties (e.g. LAI) derived from EO time series to constrain the vegetation dynamics simulated [160,164].

While EO assimilation enhances the accuracy of simulations of vegetation dynamics, challenges remain concerning input data availability (soil and detailed management practices) and scalability (many parameters), particularly for landscape or regional applications. One main limitation of EO assimilation into ecosystem models is the computational and logistical demands required to perform simulations with parameter adjustments across thousands or millions of elements (pixels or fields), often forcing a trade-off between spatial resolution and coverage.

Recent studies illustrate this dilemma when optical remote sensing data assimilation is used in ecosystem models, either privileging large-scale application [248] with a coarse resolution that is not compatible with field-scale assessments usually required in VCM or AEPs contexts or the high resolution enabling to capture intrafield variability [249–251] but limited to small areas. Despite differences in spatial and temporal scales, current applications of ecosystem models assimilating EO data remain limited to a few thousand or tens of thousands of elements (e.g. compared to ~3 million fields in France).

Moreover, model reliance on detailed input data and numerous parameters raises important issues concerning equifinality in parameter optimization, as it is not possible to separate all the processes simulated by just assimilating LAI, which reduces flexibility in capturing intrafield spatial variability. These limitations highlight the need to propose an approach that can achieve large-scale diagnostics at high resolution with few parameters while minimizing reliance on detailed management data and incorporating uncertainty indicators for the simulated variables [252–254].

An ecosystem modeling approach with parsimonious models and EO assimilation

A promising approach to assess SOC stock changes at a large scale and taking into account intrafield spatial variability in ecosystem processes consists of assimilating high-resolution EO data in an ecosystem modeling framework that combines parsimonious soil and plant models. The goal is to strike a balance between having enough processes accounted for in order to simulate the key components of the C budget to accurately estimate SOC stock changes while keeping the approach simple and scalable for large-scale applications, in line with recommendations from Paustian et al. [255] and Smith et al. [29]. Despite explicit interactions between vegetation and soil compartments (e.g. no soil water or N stress function to control plant growth), the assimilation of EO data enables accurate and objective simulations of plant development by optimizing and calibrating vegetation model parameters. Additionally, this approach allows the automatic detection and accounting of the effects of weeds, spontaneous regrowth and cover crops on SOC stock changes (e.g. [174]). Only an EO-based approach allows that. Consequently, this approach significantly reduces the reliance on extensive activity data to simulate vegetation development compared to conventional ecosystem models while implicitly accounting for the effects of many practices (e.g. mineral fertilization), stress effects (e.g. water, N , temperature), pests, diseases and extreme climatic events (e.g. hail, floods) on plant development. However, some management data (e.g. straw management, organic amendments) remain necessary to simulate SOC stock changes. Large-scale applications also require the integration of land-use maps.

The ability to apply this approach at a large scale at once, with minimal input data collection, drastically reduces the cost of implementation while having potentially high accuracy owing to the accounting for spatial variability. It offers a low cost–accuracy ratio, which makes this approach a game changer for MRV application.

Examples of parsimonious crop models adapted for this approach are GRAMI [256] and the SAFY model family (SAFY [217] and [167]; SAFY-WB [257] and [258]; SAFY-CO₂ [168]; SAFYE-CO₂ [174]) which are dedicated to upscaling crop simulations by assimilating LAI time series derived from high-resolution EO data. Biomass outputs from these models can be used as inputs for soil models to estimate SOC stock changes. For operational MRV applications, parsimonious soil models may be preferable because they require fewer parameters and input data, which reduces the risk of propagating uncertainties and the computation time for large-scale applications. As mentioned earlier concerning design strategies of soil models, Shi et al. [190] concluded based on an intercomparison exercise that adding more parameters and explicit (e.g. microbial or vertical) dynamics in the model may lead to greater uncertainties in projections,

which amplify with time and climate change. Therefore, models with fewer C pools and parameters such as RothC [179] or AMG [104] that have been robustly validated [191,192] may be great candidates, offering a good compromise between accuracy, simplicity and scalability.

However, an efficient assimilation method is essential, enabling time-efficient simulations over a large number of elements (pixels or fields), uncertainty traceability through all the simulation steps and the ability to represent uncertainties through multiple potential solutions (e.g. Bayesian calibration), as in [172]. This is crucial in environmental modeling, where different parameter sets can produce similar outputs, even though they represent very different underlying processes (i.e. equifinality in parameters).

Note that in addition to better assessment of biomass production and derived carbon inputs, high-resolution simulations enable direct comparisons between model outputs and *in situ* measurements (e.g. biomass, yield, and SOC stock changes) collected at the pixel scale (e.g. 10 × 10 m), improving the spatial representativeness and accuracy of model validation.

However, some limitations remain for the full implementation of this approach in MRV contexts, particularly the current calibration and validation methods are restricted to a limited set of crop types, whereas traditional “off-the-shelf” ecosystem models have undergone extensive development over decades for diverse management practices and pedoclimatic conditions. Additionally, the reliance on optical remote sensing data limits its application in persistently cloudy conditions, an issue that can be mitigated with a multisensor fusion strategy, as discussed later.

Hence, with further work to cover more crop types and the establishment of robust input data collection frameworks, especially for management practices and soil properties, this parsimonious modeling approach with EO assimilation offers a flexible and scalable solution. It can support a wide range of MRV applications, from national-scale reporting for NDCs to field- or pixel-scale assessments for the VCM (both “insetting” and “off-setting”) or AEPs.

This modeling approach follows the CIRCASA project's recommendations [259] to use a modular structure to derive gridded SOC stock change estimates along with associated uncertainties, and it aligns with the “system-of-systems” approach proposed by Guan et al. [222], which emphasizes the need to integrate diverse sensors, *in situ* data, and models. Current prototypes tend to adopt this strategy, such as the Retina Project [260]; Remote-C [261]; AgriCarbon-EO [172,262]; and FiON [249]. However, Soussana et al. [259] also advocate for ensembles of calibrated models rather than a single model approach.

Figures S1–S4 summarizing the pros and cons of the different Tier 3 modeling approaches are available in the Supplemental Material, as well as Table S1 summarizing their qualitative assessment. We distinguish the approaches with or without EO assimilation to highlight the benefits or limits brought by the EO assimilation. The criteria are related mainly to spatial resolution, data requirements, complexity, scalability and robustness.

All these approaches can simulate the field scale, but EO assimilation enhances spatial resolution and allows a better estimation of biomass return to the soil and its intrafield variability. The assimilation of EO data complexifies the approach (e.g. additional data and algorithms), but it is balanced with the gain of accuracy and scalability when combined with parsimonious soil or ecosystem models. The soil-centered approach (with or without EO) is the simplest approach to implement, requiring less input data, but its robustness of evaluation is limited compared to ecosystem models, which can be evaluated on several key components of the carbon budget. “Off-the-shelf” ecosystem models are generally able to represent a wide range of management practices and crop types but require more diverse and detailed input data, which increases their cost for monitoring and their computation time. The ecosystem modeling approach using parsimonious models with EO assimilation is a good compromise between complexity, scalability and robustness.

As detecting significant SOC stock changes at the field scale with soil measurements is challenging and costly [76,263], verification schemes relying on *in situ* measurements to certify carbon credits for carbon farming projects are generally restricted to project-scale verification. While this verification method improves the accuracy of the estimation, it may create inequities in the payment distribution between farmers, since all farmers receive the same credits regardless of their varying efforts and impacts. However, with approaches that assimilate EO data, annual high spatial resolution simulation allows to identify intra- and interfield patterns of carbon stock changes (see [152,172]). Therefore, having these high spatiotemporal maps of carbon stock changes and their full range of variability (intra- and interfields) may enhance the design of the sampling strategy for verification and be used instead of classical preliminary sampling schemes since most protocols require adapting the number of composite samples to SOC variability [71]. In

Figure 4. Decision tree designed to choose the SOC stock change monitoring approach according to the MRV context of application and to the local context.

addition, high resolution (e.g. 10 m resolution) improves the spatial consistency between soil samples and the spatial unit of simulation, which opens up the possibility of verifying the model's estimates at the field or farm scale with a limited number of samples and without the need to reproduce the mean SOC stock change value of the field (see Figure 37 in [36]). This approach could significantly reduce the cost of verification and may allow projects other than VCM offsetting involving large numbers of fields to be verified with soil samples. Nonetheless, verifying short-term projects (i.e. less than five years) with in situ soil measurements would be challenging and costly and might not be feasible even when building a soil sampling scheme based on high-resolution modeling approaches.

Finally, the lack of systematic uncertainty assessment remains a limitation for most approaches.

Decision tree for selecting croplands SOC monitoring approaches

This section aims to guide an MRV operator in choosing the monitoring methodology (i.e. measure/remeasure, Tier 1 to Tier 3) best suited to their purposes and local context. As previously explained, there is no “one-size-fits-all” monitoring approach optimal for all contexts of MRV. Even within a single application context (VCM, AEPs, NDCs), the selection may vary across regions (e.g. the soil types, climate, field characteristics, practices), regulatory conditions (e.g. duration of the monitoring period, required accuracy, size of the CF scheme) and resource availability (e.g. data availability and quality, existing SOC monitoring networks, locally calibrated models).

To facilitate decision-making, we built a decision tree (Figure 4) adapted from the IPCC [5] generic decision tree for identification of appropriate tiers to estimate SOC stock changes for the NDC context. We expanded and adapted the tree to accommodate the other contexts of SOC monitoring (AEPs, offsetting, insetting). The initial version and criteria for building it were discussed by 180 experts from various domains (e.g. scientists, NGOs, private companies) during two online workshops co-organized in the framework of the EU Horizon ORCaSa and MARVIC projects.

The decision tree was fine-tuned considering the six criteria as further discussed below: 1-Context of application, 2-Feasibility of *in situ* measurements of Δ SOC, 3-Suitability of modeling approaches, 4-Cost-Accuracy trade-off, 5-Compatibility of the local context with the use of EO data or not and 6-Availability of activity data (e.g. biomass, management practices). However, the final choice between specific models cannot be generalized here, as it largely depends on specific local conditions and project and verification schemes.

Context of application

Context of application (NDCs, AEPs or VCM either offsetting or insetting) is the first criterion to consider, as it shapes key elements such as the accuracy/complexity of the methods that can be considered, the spatial scale (field to national level), and the duration and frequency of the monitoring project (from one year to multiyear project). For the VCM, a distinction is made between offsetting and insetting, as offsetting projects last five years minimum, whereas insetting projects can last one year or more.

Feasibility of measure–remeasure for Δ SOC stock quantification

The second criterion of selection is whether in situ measurements of Δ SOC stock (measure–remeasure methods) are feasible, considering project duration and reporting time, sampling effort (number of samples to collect to be representative of the studied area or already existing network) and cost accuracy acceptable for the project. For short-term projects (under five years), the large number of samples required to detect significant SOC stock changes often makes this approach too costly [32,264]. However, if measure–remeasure is feasible with acceptable cost accuracy, this method is preferred. In a study by Potash et al. [32], measure–remeasure was economically feasible for projects involving more than 5000 fields with at least 5 years to remeasurement where the SOC stock changes were estimated at the project level. Otherwise, modeling approaches have to be considered.

Suitability of modeling approaches (Tiers 1 to 3)

First, the availability of a Tier 3 model adapted to the local pedoclimatic context and management practices has to be investigated, i.e. the approach should have been evaluated under these conditions and should have shown good performance. Note that whatever the Tier 3 modeling approach that will be implemented, it will require in situ data collection, such as soil information to initialize the models or key activity data (i.e. organic amendments, exported biomass: grain/tubercule, straw). Hence, at this stage of the decision process, all Tier 3 approaches are considered, from the soil-centered approach to the ecosystem approach. For NDCs, the approach must be aligned with the IPCC recommendations. For the other contexts (VCMs, AEPs), some projects can involve only one field of the farm; therefore, in this case, the spatial resolution of the approach must be at least at the field level.

If no Tier 3 approach is suitable (calibrated/validated) for the local context under consideration, possible alternatives depend on the context of application:

- (i) For NDCs, a Tier 2 approach can be considered following IPCC guidelines and must be adapted to the local pedo-climatic context and practices. If no Tier 2 changes are available and SOC stock changes in croplands are not a *key category* in the country according to the IPCC, then Tier 1 changes can be considered. Otherwise, more accurate and reliable methods need to be implemented (i.e. measure–remeasure, Tier 2 or Tier 3). Hence, the financial question and trade-off between cost and accuracy arise to determine whether it is preferable i) to invest in a national SOC stock monitoring network or ii) to collect data for developing a Tier 2 method or iii) for (developing) calibrating and validating a Tier 3 method adapted to this local context.
- (ii) For the AEPs MRV context, according to the established rules, Tier 2 might be considered. For instance, the H2020 NIVA EU project proposed a Tier 2 approach for the CAP. If no Tier 2 data are available, the total cost and cost accuracy of measure–remeasure of Δ SOC stock should be compared to those of collecting the necessary data for developing a Tier 2 method or for (developing) calibrating and validating a Tier 3 method.
- (iii) For offsetting and insetting in VCM contexts, Tier 2 is not considered; thus, when no Tier 3 approach is available, the consideration of the cost and cost accuracy of performing the measure–remeasure of Δ SOC stocks and of collecting data for (developing) calibrating and validating Tier 3 approaches arises. As mentioned before, offsetting projects are a minimum of five years long, while insetting projects can last only one year. In this case, if no Tier 3 approach is available, the cost of the Δ SOC stock measure–remeasure and its accuracy could be prohibitive compared to calibrating and validating an already existing Tier 3 model to the local context.

Cost-Accuracy trade-off

The questions regarding the profitability of an investment to develop an approach over another and the possibility to reuse approaches for other applications and projects highlights the need for scalable,

parsimonious and transposable approaches that minimize overparameterization and avoid excessive reliance on highly local-specific data.

Compatibility with the use of Earth observation (EO) data

When Tier 3 approaches are identified as the best option, the next criterion is the compatibility of the local context with the use of EO data. The possibility of using EO data depends first on the size of the fields when considering satellite data (not relevant for drones): the monitored fields should be large enough compared to the satellite's data resolution (considering that a one-to-two-pixel buffer should be applied along the contours of the field), the topography of the field should not be too complex (to avoid errors in projection or surface reflectance correction), and no physical element (e.g. trees, electric pylons or their shadow) should disturb the observations of the field from the satellite. It also depends on the ability and frequency of observing the surface; e.g. for optical satellites, cloud coverage should not be too long during vegetation development. Finally, the geospatial contour of fields should be available, especially in contexts of application where monitoring is conducted at the field or farm level (e.g. AEP, offsetting and insetting). Then, when all those conditions are met, it's preferable to use Tier 3 modeling approaches combined with EO, such as soil-centered approaches using carbon inputs from biomass derived from remote sensing products or parsimonious ecosystem modeling approaches that are more prone to EO data assimilation for their scalability and time efficiency than strong coupling ecosystem approaches.

If the use of EO data is not possible, Tier 3 approaches can still be considered, and the selection within Tier 3 approaches will depend on available data.

Availability of activity data

- (i) For NDCs, the accuracy and need for field-specific activity data are lower compared to the other context of MRV, allowing the use of regional statistics as input to Tier 3 approaches, such as biomass production and management practices. It then relaxes the need to collect specific activity data. Hence, a soil-centered approach can be used that relies on regional statistics of biomass production and management practices, as well as ecosystem modeling approaches using "off-the-shelf" ecosystem models with simplified assumptions to represent average crop rotations or management practices. However, we can assume that there are often parts of the countries where EO-based approaches are applicable, raising the question of spatial consistency regarding the methodology used.
- (ii) For AEPs, we could expect reliable detailed activity data (e.g. yield and activity data verified by an agricultural advisor) at the field scale (preferably through FMIS) to be provided by the farmer, since they may have been declared formerly in order to be eligible for subsidies. Under these circumstances, soil-centered approaches could be used as well as ecosystem modeling approaches based on "off-the-shelf" ecosystem models. If this assumption is revealed to be false (no yield and/or no detailed activity data available at the field scale), the question whether or not it is possible to use a Tier 2 approach may arise. If the answer is no (for example, because this is not envisaged by the paying agencies), then the question of acquiring new data will arise (for measure-remeasure or for developing new Tier 2 or Tier 3 methods).
- (iii) For the VCM offsetting and insetting contexts, if the use of EO data is not possible, then the choice of approaches will depend on the availability of biomass and detailed activity data. In the case where biomass data are available (e.g. *in situ* measurement or yield declared by farmers), the soil-centered approach may be preferred for its ease of implementation. If no *in situ* biomass data are available but detailed activity data are available, then it is preferable to use an ecosystem modeling approach using "off-the-shelf" ecosystem models able to represent vegetation growth. Finally, if detailed activity data are not available, a plant model requiring less activity data (than "off-the-shelf" ecosystem models) can be used to estimate biomass production and derive carbon inputs from biomass residues to feed a soil-centered approach.

Essential improvements for the future

Our analysis of the different SOC stock change monitoring approaches highlights the need for improvements in several application and evaluation areas. These essential improvements are required to ensure both scientific robustness and successful implementation of these approaches in the MRV context and in operational conditions.

Improving monitoring methodology

The improvements are categorized based on their primary objectives: increasing the accuracy and reliability of the approaches and facilitating their implementation under operational conditions within various MRV frameworks. It is worth noting that many of these improvements contribute simultaneously to multiple goals.

For better accuracy and reliability

Innovation around scalable cost-effective soil measurements

Conventional soil sampling and lab analysis methods can be costly, potentially prohibiting the measure–remeasure approach [265] or proper initialization of models. While monitoring approaches should integrate existing soil data sources when available, alternative soil sensing methods, either in the laboratory, in the field, or from a remote platform (handheld, on-the-go, UAV, airplane, satellite), could be a cost-effective option to support monitoring approaches [266]. By either providing a pattern of SOC content variability to improve the sampling location allocation strategy [267] or enabling many more measurements at lower cost [268]. Although conventional soil sampling/measurements are still needed for the calibration of any sensing method, the number of these samples may decrease while maintaining overall accuracy and increasing the number of observations of a soil property spatially. Proximal sensing can provide a good balance between cost and accuracy [269].

Spectroscopy of the visible, near- and mid-infrared parts of the electromagnetic spectrum (Vis-NIR, NIR, MIR) can be used to estimate total SOC content, SOC fractions, soil texture and additional soil properties [62,270–272]. Initiatives to build soil spectral calibration libraries with associated estimation methodologies at regional or global scale [272–274]; Soils4Africa project³), the creation of large calibration datasets (USDA-KSSL [275], LUCAS⁴) and innovative algorithms for spectral estimation of soil properties (CIFOR-ICRAF⁵, Eurofins⁶) are promising solutions towards more affordable soil property measurements.

In-field measurements using Vis-NIR or MIR spectroscopy from platforms are often not accurate enough at present for SOC change detection or mapping small differences in space or time [276], although the 2021 Australian Soil C method [21,77] allowed their use for estimating SOC concentration. This is probably the only method that currently supports this technology. Several companies operating MRV procedures for SOC projects in Australia heavily rely on IR spectroscopy.

For large scale monitoring programs, both MIR and Vis-NIR estimates are accepted as appropriate methods to measure SOC concentrations like in the Rapid Carbon Assessment Project in the USA [277], and the Australian Carbon Farming Initiative [77,278], and present EU LUCAS topsoil sampling rounds [279,280].

In-field gamma ray spectrometry, either passive or active, has emerged recently as a promising technology to operationally measure soil properties for MRV purposes. Passive gamma-ray spectrometry enables spatial quantification of soil texture patterns, large spatial distributions of soil organic matter differences, and spatially static soil moisture differences over time. Passive gamma-ray spectrometry is mostly applied on-the-go and is a good quantitative predictor of soil texture fractions if calibrated. Owing to the attenuation of gamma radiation by matter, 95% of the signal typically originates from the 0–30 cm topsoil layer [281,282].

On the other hand, active gamma-ray spectrometry is used for soil bulk density sensing, electromagnetic induction for soil texture, bulk density and salinity measurements combined [283], and in some cases, penetration resistance is used as a proxy for differences in density or potential for root growth. Active gamma-ray spectrometry is currently mostly applied to cores extracted from the soil [284] or to probes inserted in the soil (~1 m depth) [285] to measure the bulk density of the soil in g cm^{-3} , including the moisture content at the time of measurement. The measurement is fast, in-field and can be conducted along the soil profile in 5 cm increments with an accuracy that is slightly lower than that of conventional methods (e.g. Kopecky rings) for bulk density measurements. A correction for soil moisture content is needed to retrieve dry bulk density, which can be done using a soil moisture sensor or VNIR measurements [285].

Decision support tools and literature reviews for proximal sensing, including spectroscopy and gamma ray, are in development and available to assist in the selection of techniques for different purposes [286–288].

Systematic uncertainty assessment

A major limitation of current MRV approaches reliability is the absence of standardized procedures for the quantification of uncertainties, as pointed out in [289]. Their recommendation, which originally concerned crop and ecosystem modeling, should be extended to the overall SOC monitoring procedure in MRV contexts. This means focusing effort to standardize uncertainty quantification and include it systematically in the monitoring process. This approach ensures that end-users can assess whether the monitoring approach is reliable and suitable for specific applications in conformity with IPCC recommendations. It also emphasizes that holistic uncertainty propagation should be considered, including uncertainty related to the design of the baseline to assess the uncertainty associated with the SOC stock change estimation properly. In the case of measure–remeasure, a holistic approach to uncertainty assessment should consider sample acquisition, sample preparation, laboratory or field analysis, along with the uncertainty of the ancillary data and algorithms used to produce spatially representative quantifications. In the case of modeling approaches, it should consider all the modeling workflow, from input data – including activity data, soil data, and forcing data – to model uncertainty. As mentioned previously, probabilistic methods for data assimilation offer a robust framework for uncertainty quantification, as it allows to estimate probabilistic distribution of variables and parameters. Using ensemble modeling is also an option to account for uncertainties in model structure.

The multimodel ensemble approach can be an effective strategy to reduce structural uncertainty. An intercomparison of eight models widely used, Palosuo et al. [244] showed that under data-limited conditions, individual models struggled to accurately predict yields without calibration, but the multimodel mean predictions aligned well with the observations. This is also confirmed by ensemble simulations that have been assessed for carbon fluxes [290] and for SOC [129,212,291,292].

Representing accurate mean and spatial variability of carbon inputs to the soil from biomass residues

For Tier 3 modeling approaches, improving the accuracy and reliability of biomass estimations is essential, given its key role in determining carbon inputs to the soil. A sensitivity analysis with the AMG soil model [102] identified uncertainties in cover crop biomass as one of the major sources of error when estimating the differential SOC stock between two management scenarios. Accurate assessment of biomass production requires accounting for spatial and temporal variability in photosynthesis capacity [222], as ignoring this can lead to significant errors, up to 21% according to Luo et al. [293]. It also requires consideration of the effect of stress factors on vegetation dynamics (e.g. water or nutrients), the impact of pests and diseases on biomass production, extreme climatic events (e.g. tornadoes, floods), and spontaneous regrowth and weeds [168,174,175] on soil carbon inputs. High-resolution EO data, particularly from constellations such as Sentinel-2 (10–20 m resolution) and Landsat-8, offer an effective mean to account for these factors and capture biomass intrafield spatial variability at low cost. For instance, Wijmer et al. [172] show that assimilating high-resolution GLAI data instead of mean-field-level GLAI data reduces bias by 5% and avoids underestimation of uncertainty by 37% in winter wheat biomass estimation. When none of the existing models is adapted to the conditions (e.g. crop type or pedoclimatic conditions), EO data-driven approaches trained and tested on in situ biomass datasets can be a cost-effective alternative, as the calibration relies only on in situ biomass [123,124]. However, these approaches should be considered with care when transposing to regions and conditions not covered by the training datasets.

Improving EO robustness with multisensor strategies

As mentioned in the EO section (Section 2.3.2), each remote sensing technology presents opportunities to better inform the MRV scheme but also has its own limitations. The fusion of multisensor data to enhance biogeophysical variable retrieval and emerging solutions of multivariable assimilation in crop modeling presents a great opportunity to maximize the information from EO and reduce drawbacks. For instance, to address the constraint of cloud-free optical images for Tier 3 modeling based on EO approaches, adoption of multiple spectral domains and technologies by combining, for instance optical multispectral satellite data (Sentinel-2) with SAR data (Sentinel-1). The latter is slightly sensitive to cloud cover (although it is impacted by extreme rain events), meaning that it can be used to fill gaps in vegetation index time series [294,295] or to produce proxy biomass for multivariable assimilation [296–298]. This can improve the transposability of Tier 3 modeling approaches based on optical EO data to cloudy regions.

Regarding EO data reliability, the development of hybrid approaches that combine the physical robustness of RTM with the data-driven capabilities of machine learning techniques shows significant potential for improving parameter retrievals and reducing uncertainty in biophysical products such as GLAI [299].

For easiness of implementation

Simplified quantification approaches for stakeholder engagement

SOC stock change quantification is just one brick in the implementation of the complex framework of an MRV scheme for SOC. While implementation of the practices by the farmers is the most important element, the investment in terms of time and financing of SOC monitoring are of particular concern, acting as barriers to the implementation of a CF project [300].

Then, it is important to consider whether the monitoring method is easy and quick to implement by an actor aiming at running an MRV. Implementations should refer here to the full process, including understanding the method through training and documentation, installing or configuring it, and running it operationally. Note that an engineering-wise complex but accurate method such as a deep learning model or an ecosystem model with assimilation may be rendered easy and practical to implement if a well-designed user experience (UX) [301] with associated tools (e.g. graphical interface) is provided. The level of automation of the processes when implementing a method is also a good criterion to define its ease of use and practicality (e.g. automated data gathering through APIs).

Augmenting the collection of activity data

The availability, accuracy and accessibility of activity data are critical factors determining the ease of implementation of a monitoring approach based on Tier 3: the more activity data that need to be collected “manually” (e.g. through farmer’s survey), the more expensive and time-consuming it will be. Even if efforts are made to minimize the reliance of modeling on detailed activity data, such as using parsimonious modeling with EO assimilation, a minimum set of key information on management remains needed. Accordingly, monitoring approaches based on Tier 3 should leverage existing data sources already gathered by regional authorities, CAP reporting, or data collected by farmers, such as soil data. Additionally, the integration of new automatically accessible data streams such as FMIS offers a promising way to reduce manual effort if quality and consistency are checked.

More generally, reducing data acquisition costs (e.g. soil data, activity data), including time and logistic costs associated, is crucial for the economic viability of monitoring, especially for large-scale applications. In this context, open-source EO data (e.g. Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2) offer a powerful solution to reduce data acquisition costs for management, as previously mentioned, key agricultural practices can be retrieved (e.g. land use, cover crop: [148,149], tillage: [153], fraction of residue: [157], etc.), while providing high temporal and spatial resolution over large areas. Although their integration into the SOC monitoring approach is, for now, most robust in vegetation monitoring, recent studies highlight promising future applications, including the detection of organic amendment applications [158,159] or the estimation of surface SOC content [141], as discussed in the previous section.

Improving scalability

The technical scalability of the method is also a determining criterion that goes in parallel with the scalability in terms of financing schemes and policy framework across MRV contexts such as the AEPs (e.g. CAP), the NDCs (when relying on Tier 3 approaches) or some large CF projects. Technical scalability addresses the capacity to provide accurate estimates over large regions at high resolution while maintaining manageable computational demands and propagation of uncertainty [29,172]. The optimization of data assimilation schemes, the parameterization of models, and the minimization of input requirements are key to achieving this balance. Future modeling efforts should carefully account for the scale dependence of mathematical formulations, especially when they are applied to a wide range of scales [302], and address the continuous increase in validation against field observations [191]. With the development of data-driven methods, hybrid approaches, such as machine learning combined with process-based modeling or surrogate models, are also expected to play an increasing role. While these approaches raise important questions about transparency and interpretability, they are already developing rapidly in the climate science community [303].

Towards a harmonized monitoring approach for hybrid incentive schemes in SOC sequestration

Finally, developing monitoring tools that can be applied in different contexts of MRV is essential to ensure consistency between the SOC stock change assessments performed in those different contexts and could allow to build a consistent and unique field-level carbon registry (as foreseen in the EU CRCF). Such harmonized monitoring tools will reinforce the accreditation credibility of monitoring approaches and increase farmers’ involvement by reducing the need to develop and manage separate systems for each

policy or project. Doing so would allow the creation of a hybrid scheme where farmers would obtain a part of the payment based on actions to increase SOC stocks as well as payments based on results [304]. In such a hybrid scheme, the farmer and policy body share the risk of nondelivery (i.e. no carbon storage in the soil), which might be more efficient, as suggested by Raina et al. [300].

Improving evaluation process of the methodologies

Evaluate models in operational contexts

One key priority is the systematic evaluation of models and approaches in operational contexts beyond controlled agronomic trials [305]. Most of the models (soil, crop or ecosystem) used for SOC monitoring have been developed, calibrated and validated based on long term experiments (e.g. Rothamsted trials; [95]) and sometimes on SOC monitoring networks (e.g. LUCAS in Europe; see [67]) or flux tower networks (e.g. Fluxnet; [110]). However, the current evaluation reveals major limitations to represent farm conditions, assess comprehensive carbon budget components and ensure robust performance for large-scale applications.

To date, few model evaluations have incorporated a comprehensive assessment of the components of the carbon cycle (biomass, CO₂ fluxes, etc.; e.g. [168]), and the resulting SOC stock changes, and even fewer under operational monitoring conditions [172,243,249]. Regional observatories combining soil and vegetation sampling at farms, flux measurements with eddy covariance flux towers and surveys on field management such as the Regional Space Observatory⁷ and the Field Observatory Network⁸ are extremely valuable. Yet, the representativeness of these datasets is limited with respect to the diversity of farm practices, soil types, and climatic conditions. Moreover, the accuracy of the input data from highly instrumented sites will necessarily be better than that of data available in an operational context. As a result, depending on model sensitivity, the models that perform best in an experimental context may not be the best in an operational context.

Except for a few fields equipped with flux towers (e.g. the ICOS network in Europe), there is currently no regional or global observation infrastructure that collects data to monitor SOC stock changes simultaneously with biomass and management data, allowing us to interpret the evolution of SOC stocks. Even soil monitoring networks such as LUCAS [67] lack key information on field management and biomass inputs to the soil to fully interpret the SOC trends observed. Hence, their use to develop, train or evaluate models is limited or requires strong assumptions.

This calls for the deployment of an international network to monitor SOC, biomass and management practices, including at farms, allowing to evaluate monitoring approaches based on modeling in an operational context of MRV. Preferably, this network would integrate existing flux and soil monitoring networks such as LUCAS or EO monitoring networks like JECAM⁹ [306].

Reinforcement and standardization of the model's evaluation for SOC monitoring

Beyond the need for more representative observational data, there is a critical need to evaluate and compare the performances of different modeling approaches (e.g. using the same datasets), particularly to test and refine the assumptions underlying the decision tree. For example, in data-scarce contexts, it remains unclear whether relying on simpler models, which require fewer inputs, is more accurate and robust than applying more complex models with default values or simplified inputs to compensate for missing data [307]. Accordingly, data collected and feedback regarding monitoring and verification from already implemented MRV programs and MRV tools represent highly valuable information that should be included in the development and improvement of monitoring approaches and their evaluation from an operational perspective.

Additionally, multimodel ensemble evaluations are essential to assess their performances under varying environmental and data conditions, and particularly in conditions where no single model is adapted, to demonstrate whether a multimodel ensemble can be a solution when no suitable model exists or is available. Such comparative analyses are crucial to guide model choice and increasing confidence in SOC stock change estimates in diverse operational MRV settings.

Conclusion

This study aligns with current efforts to identify adequate methodologies to monitor SOC stock changes in croplands at the European Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming regulation level and from national initiatives (e.g. low-carbon labels).

The task of accurately monitoring SOC stock changes in croplands presents considerable and diverse challenges. There is a growing demand for cost-effective, large-scale, and continuous SOC monitoring methods that necessitate approaches beyond traditional measurement–remeasurement and modeling techniques. Our study highlights that remote sensing, particularly for vegetation monitoring, already offers mature applications that can help quantify biomass restitution to the soil for modeling purposes. Additionally, emerging remote sensing approaches show promise for more detailed mapping of soil property changes and for verifying the adoption and persistence of recommended carbon farming practices, thereby supporting the development of cost-effective and scalable SOC monitoring strategies.

This paper explores the different approaches available for monitoring SOC stock changes in croplands, considering their strengths and limitations. By evaluating these SOC monitoring approaches with respect to their context of application, we provide guidance for selecting the most suitable methodologies, using decision trees. We identified key criteria for aligning monitoring approaches with current needs and adaptation for the future. Implementing the decision tree in an operational web platform remains a considerable challenge. This study confirmed that there are currently no fit-for-all-purpose methodological approaches for monitoring and verifying SOC stock changes in arable land, while it recommends the use of measure–remeasure and parsimonious Tier 3 modeling approaches with Earth observations when possible. However, it also highlights the inadequacy of a measure–remeasure approach for short-term projects (<5 years), relying on field or farm-level monitoring, which excludes most insetting projects within VCM and AEPs initiatives.

Building on this review and Batjes et al. [11], an important next step will be to assess SOC monitoring methodologies for other ecosystems, such as grasslands and forests, with the aim of developing a modular, multi-ecosystem decision tree for SOC monitoring.

Endnotes

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Disclosure statement

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ORCID

Ainhoa Ihasusta 0009-0006-9767-1581
Ahmad Al Bitar 0000-0002-1756-1096
Niels H. Batjes 0000-0003-2367-3067
Fenny van Egmond 0000-0002-2608-9889
Rémi Cardinael 0000-0002-9924-3269
Senani Karunaratne 0000-0002-9278-7941
Pierre Barré 0000-0002-0822-0556
Ludovic Arnaud 0000-0002-6106-7589
Gerard Heuvelink 0000-0003-0959-9358
Ben Macdonald 0000-0001-8105-0779
Taeken Wijmer 0000-0001-6134-2811
Julien Demenois 0000-0002-2271-8465
Cloé Paul-Victor 0000-0001-5413-8046
Eric Ceschia 0000-0001-5941-752X

Data availability statement

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article and its supplementary materials.

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